

Form to Help with RDI Data Appraisal

This report presents the draft of a form that can be used to help appraise and assess the value of research, development & innovation (RDI) data. The form was created as part of the Data Steward training at Tampere University. The aim of this project work was to develop a tool for the RDI staff of Metropolia University of Applied Sciences to support the appraisal of RDI data, and to facilitate the identification of opportunities for further use of the data, as well as factors limiting its further use. The project work was supervised by Joonas Koironen from Metropolia UAS.

In this report, I present the criteria for determining the value of research data collected as background information, as well as the creation process of the form and its contents.

Background: Research Data Appraisal

To create the form, various criteria and materials related to research data appraisal and value assessment were collected. Most sources dealt specifically with the long-term preservation and archiving of research data. The focus of this project was broader than long-term preservation, since in the target organisation of the test form there is also a need to identify data that should be preserved in the medium term and could be further used. Identifying RDI data and its value is not always easy; data may not necessarily be perceived as the result of an RDI project, unlike publications. Despite the different perspectives, the criteria for long-term preservation also provided useful insights for the development of the form tool.

When comparing the questions and criteria used in research data appraisal in various sources, seven key themes were identified: significance, uniqueness, reuse purposes, quality of data and documentation, obstacles to preservation and further use, cost factors and funder requirements. The following table presents examples of some of the criteria for data appraisal and preservation related to these perspectives.

Significance of data	<p>Could the data relate to a discovery or a significant new research process (DCC 2014)</p> <p>The significance of the task (research) and the importance of its operating environment in society (Kansallisarkisto 2020)</p> <p>The significance to research over time and to society through research impacts; the historical and cultural significance (Lehtisalo ym. 2023)</p> <p>Data depicting change or a turning point (Näreaho & Koironen 2020)</p> <p>Societal, economic and academic impact (Talvinen 2019)</p>
Uniqueness of data	<p>Would reproducing the data be difficult, costly, or impossible (DCC 2014)</p> <p>The uniqueness of the information in relation to other archived data (Kansallisarkisto 2020)</p> <p>Scientific and cultural uniqueness (Lehtisalo ym. 2023)</p> <p>Could re-collecting similar data be ethically questionable (Näreaho & Koironen 2020)</p>
Reuse purposes	<p>Verification, further analysis and publications, learning and teaching (DCC 2014)</p> <p>The ease of use of the information, its compatibility with other information, and its diverse application possibilities across various scientific and research fields as well as in non-research contexts (Kansallisarkisto 2020)</p> <p>Usage within different fields of research, the amount of unanalysed information (Lehtisalo ym. 2023)</p> <p>Compatibility with other data, versatile application possibilities, added value (Näreaho & Koironen 2020)</p>

Quality of data and documentation	<p>Completeness, sample size, accuracy, validity, reliability, representativeness (DCC 2014)</p> <p>Geographical, temporal, or target group coverage of the data, and its usability: logical structure and metadata related to the data lifecycle (Kansallisarkisto 2020)</p> <p>The repeatability of the research, quality assurance (Lehtisalo ym. 2023)</p> <p>Quality and reliability, descriptive metadata and comprehensibility, coverage, adherence to the FAIR principles (Näreaho & Koironen 2020)</p> <p>Accuracy, precision, consistency, timeliness, comprehensiveness, understandability (metadata), machine readability, access rights (Tarkoma ym. 2023)</p>
Obstacles to preservation and further use	<p>Consent agreement does not allow data to be reused or archived, anonymisation not feasible (DCC 2014)</p> <p>Sensitivity or contractual or copyright terms restrict public access or reuse (DCC 2014)</p> <p>Problems related to agreements on authorship, preservation or access rights, informing research participants, or anonymisation possibilities (Näreaho & Koironen 2020)</p>
Cost factors	<p>Is there sufficient funding for data management and storage (DCC 2014)</p> <p>Cost factors including compliance with standards, recommendations, and agreed-upon file formats; determining retention requirements; and the regular disposal of data subject to retention periods (Kansallisarkisto 2020)</p> <p>Investments and work resources, commercial value (Lehtisalo ym. 2023)</p>
Funder requirements	<p>Does the funder recommend sharing data (DCC 2014)</p> <p>The interests of the research funder (Lehtisalo ym. 2023)</p> <p>Funding terms of public funders (Näreaho & Koironen 2020)</p>

Implementation: Creating the Form

Given the project timeline, it was not possible to build a completely new tool from scratch, so the plan was to implement a pilot version using an existing form tool. The options available in Metropolia were Microsoft Forms, Google Forms, and E-lomake (Formjack). Out of these E-lomake proved to be the most flexible option and was selected for creating the pilot version.

Some ideas for technical implementation were drawn from the test version of the RISK-I tool by the University of Helsinki, which is an application for international collaboration risk assessment (Laitinen 2025). The application uses a color-coded system (green-yellow-red) to indicate different risk levels from 1 to 3. This pilot form utilizes a similar coding system: each response receives feedback indicating whether the data could or should be preserved (green), some issue must be checked or paid attention to enable preservation (yellow), or the issue prevents preservation (red). The questions were formulated using research data appraisal criteria found from the source material, as well as knowledge of the organisational practices accumulated through data management support service work.

Some technical limitations of the tools restricted the implementation of the pilot version of the form. For example, none of the three form tools allowed for assigning points to different responses or basing the feedback on a point total, unless the responses were marked as correct or incorrect like test answers. In E-lomake tool, it is possible to add explanatory text and define dependencies between fields, so that specific text feedback is displayed when a specific response option is selected. This was chosen as the implementation method for the form. There were still issues with generating and saving the final summary, as it was not possible to include only the texts that appear based on the selected answers; instead, all texts would have been included. The implementation of these ideas remained a topic for further development after the project work.

Result: The Pilot Version of the Form

The first version of the form was created in Finnish and in English. The form begins with questions that help assess the value of the data and its potential for reuse and concludes with questions that help identify potential obstacles and risks related to preservation and reuse of the data. Some of the questions include explanatory text that provides a more detailed information on the topic of the question. The goal was to ensure that the questions and the feedback provided for the answers would be easy to understand. The feedback includes the colour coding, a brief evaluation and guidance text, and, where necessary, links to organisation's own or more general guidelines. The texts included in the form are presented as an appendix at the end of this report.

The form exists also as a test version than can be used

- in Finnish: <https://elomake.metropolia.fi/lomakkeet/47296/lomake.html>
- in English: https://elomake.metropolia.fi/lomakkeet/47296/lomake.html?rinnakkaislomake=english_test

The username and the password of the form is test.

Conclusion

There is potential for further development of the form. Due to the limitations of the current tool, it would be useful to investigate whether it would be possible, based on the pilot version and by utilising open-source code, to implement a separate tool that would not be dependent on E-lomake features. This would improve functionality and enable the form to be developed into a more user-friendly and versatile application. The form could then be developed to be technically similar to the RISK-I application by the University of Helsinki. Within the timeframe of this project, it was not yet possible to organise user testing of the pilot version. An important next step is therefore to ask RDI staff to test the form and to collect feedback and development suggestions.

References

DCC (2014). *Five steps to decide what data to keep: a checklist for appraising research data v.1*. Digital Curation Centre. <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/guidance/how-guides/five-steps-decide-what-data-keep>

Kansallisarkisto (2020). *Arvonmääritys- ja seulontapolitiikka. Versio 1.6 16.12.2020*. <https://kansallisarkisto.fi/documents/141232930/149322637/Arvonm%C3%A4%C3%A4ritys-+ja+seulontapolitiikka+versio+1.6..pdf>

Laitinen, Markus (2025). *RISK-I: HY kv-toiminnan riskienarvioinnin ja -hallinnan työkalu*. Esitys Finn-ARMA-verkoston webinaarissa 14.3.2025. https://wiki.eduuni.fi/download/attachments/141988813/Risk-i_FinnARMA_webinaari_140325.pdf

Lehtisalo, A., Asmi, A., Troberg, H. Parland-von Essen, J., Hakala, J., Laine, K., Söderholm, M., Vuorinen, M., Virtanen, M., Salminen, N., Nygren, P., Huuskonen, S., Sipponen, S., Lindholm, T., Mäkinen, T., Taskinen, T., Rosti, T., Alaterä, T., Pääkkönen, T. & Koivula, H. (2023). *Improve the quality and impact of your research through data management - A guide for making your data FAIR*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8012377>

Näreaho, S. & Koiranen, J. (2020). *Minkälainen tutkimusaineisto kannattaisi tallentaa uudelleenkäyttöä varten?* Metropolia Ammattikorkeakoulu. <https://blogit.metropolia.fi/tikissa/2020/10/01/minkalainen-tutkimusaineisto-kannattaisi-tallentaa-uudelleenkaaytoa-varten/>

Talvinen, K. (2019). *Digital Preservation (Fairdata-PAS): Guidelines for UH Evaluators*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5785971>

Tarkoma, J., Jakobsson, A., Haakana, M., Kosonen, J. & Ranki, J. (2023). *Tiedon laatukriteerit ja mittaristo – soveltamisohje*. Tilastokeskus. https://stat.fi/media/uploads/org/tilastokeskus/tiedonlaatu/tiedon_laatukriteerien_soveltamisohje.pdf

Appendix: The Contents of the Form

Title: Data appraisal: should the data be preserved?

Preface:

This form helps you to assess the value of research data. By answering the questions, you will receive guidance on whether the data should be preserved after the project has ended.

Research data covers all collected or produced material on which the project's results are based (such as measurement results, samples, surveys, interviews, collected materials, research diaries, workshop materials, feedback, software, information models - excluding publications).

Explanations of symbols used:

(alt text: OK) The data is reusable and for this part and should or could be preserved.

(alt text: Check) Stop to make sure that this part is done correctly so that the data will be reusable and can be preserved.

(alt text: Stop) The data cannot be reused or preserved due to this issue.

Select all statements that apply to the data:

- The data can be reused in future projects
- The data can be combined with other datasets (e.g., to expand or supplement other data, or to serve as a point of comparison)
- The data can be used in teaching (e.g., as learning material or in student projects)
- The data could have commercial value (e.g., reuse in business cooperation or commercial applications)
- Recollecting or reproducing the data would be difficult or impossible
- The data has economic value and requires significant resources to produce
- The data is socially, culturally, historically, or developmentally significant, unique, or influential.
- None of the above

When one or more statements, except for the last one, have been selected:

The data can be reused. The more options selected, the more valuable and widely usable the data is, and the more important it is to preserve it. Complete the form to see if the other preservation criteria are also met.

When the second-to-last option is selected:

The data is particularly valuable and should be preserved for the long term. Long-term preservation is possible for higher education institutions using CSC's PAS service. Complete the form to ensure that other preservation criteria are also met and contact data support to implement long-term preservation.

When "None of the above" is selected:

Since there is no reuse potential, it is likely not necessary to preserve the data.

Can the data be potentially reused outside of Metropolia, too?

- Yes
- No, only within Metropolia

When "yes" is selected:

- It is recommended to open the data in a data repository or data archive, e.g.
 - CSC's Fairdata services
 - Zenodo
 - a subject-specific data archive (for data of international interest)

Data Support can assist you in opening your data and selecting a suitable data archive.

When "no" is selected:

It is recommended to preserve the data in Metta, which is an internal repository for research data in Metropolia. See the instructions on intranet.

Does the project funder require that the data or part of it is preserved or opened?

- Yes / possibly
- No

When "yes" is selected:

Follow the funder's guidelines. Examples of some research funders' policies regarding the openness of research results: [Research Council of Finland](#), [Horizon Europe](#), [Business Finland](#)

When "no" is selected:

Does not prevent preservation

Is the data described in a way that makes it understandable? Select all statements that apply:

Explanation: Data description, or metadata, tells the contextual information on how the material was produced, what it contains, and how it has been processed.

- The data is described according to a metadata standard or format for the field of research.
- The data is described using Metropolia's metadata model (in an accompanying README file).
- The data is described in a research diary or other documentation file.
- The data files include descriptive information (such as background information or explanations of variables and abbreviations).
- The description is not sufficient for the data to be understandable to other users.

When one or more statements, except for the last one, have been selected:

A sufficient description makes the data understandable and enables its reuse. Instructions for data description can be found in the [Guide to Research Data Management](#). You can also ask the Data Support Services for help with data description.

When the last option is selected:

Without sufficient description the data is not understandable or possible to reuse. Instructions for data description can be found in the [Guide to Research Data Management](#). You can also ask the Data Support Services for help with data description.

Is the data accurate and reliable?

Explanation: Accuracy means that no data content has been lost and that the integrity of the data has not been compromised e.g., due to data processing, data transfer, or measurement errors.

- Yes
- No

When "yes" is selected:

Does not prevent preservation

When "no" is selected:

It is not worthwhile to preserve data if it is not accurate and reliable.

Are the storage costs of data high?

Explanation: Large datasets require a lot of storage space.

- Yes
- No
- I'm not sure

When "yes" is selected:

 Weigh the storage costs against the benefits of the data. If the material is widely reusable and valuable, higher costs do not prevent preservation. You can assess the value of the data using the first question on this form.

When "no" is selected:

 Does not prevent preservation

When "I'm not sure" is selected:

 Costs may arise, for example, from

- the storage space required for large datasets
- if non-free software is required for the (further) use of the data
- maintenance of permanently preserved data (e.g., conversion of obsolete file formats into functional ones, maintenance of data integrity, and protection against damage)

Weigh the storage costs against the benefits of the data. If the material is widely reusable and valuable, higher costs do not prevent preservation. You can assess the value of the data using the first question on this form.

Is the data owned by Metropolia?

Explanation: Data ownership is agreed with possible cooperation partners. At Metropolia, the ownership rights to the data have been transferred to Metropolia mainly through employment contracts, or separate rights transfer agreement, if needed.

- Yes
- The data ownership is joint with other cooperation partners
- No / The ownership is unclear

When "yes" is selected:

 Does not prevent preservation

When the second option is selected:

 Make a written agreement on the terms of joint ownership and include the preservation and/or opening of the data.

When "no" is selected:

 Obstacles and uncertainties concerning ownership or agreements prevent reuse of the data.

Is the data of part of it protected by copyright or other intellectual property rights?

Explanation: Includes e.g. images or texts produced by the research subjects, or software or products produced in the project for commercial use.

- Yes
- No

When "yes" is selected:

 If the research subjects have copyrights to the data they produce, their consent must be obtained for the storage, opening, or reuse of the data. Uncertainties concerning intellectual property rights prevent the reuse of the material.

When "no" is selected:

 Does not prevent preservation

Is data collected from individuals participating in the study or from organizations requiring research permits?

- Yes
- No

When "no" is selected:

Does not prevent preservation

When "yes" is selected, a follow-up question:

How is the use of the data after the end of the project described in the participant information sheet and/or the organization's research permit?

- The data or parts of it will be preserved for further use.
- The data or parts of it will be opened in anonymized form.
- The data will be destroyed in its entirety.

When one of the first two options has been selected:

Data can be preserved or opened once participants have been informed and consent has been obtained.

When the last option is selected:

If the participant information sheet and/or the research permit states that the collected data will be destroyed, it cannot be preserved or reused. If you wish to preserve the data, you must request permissions again.

Does the data contain personal or sensitive information?

Explanation: Sensitive information includes, for example, trade secrets, sensitive location data, information related to dual-use products, and other confidential information.

- Yes
- No

When "no" is selected:

Does not prevent preservation

When "yes" is selected, a follow-up question:

Is it possible to anonymize the data or remove sensitive information in such a way that the data remains usable?

- Yes
- No

When "yes" is selected:

Anonymized data may be preserved or opened if participants have been informed and consent has been obtained. [Finnish Social Sciences Data Archive](#) provides instructions for anonymization.

When "no" is selected:

If it is not possible to anonymize the data and remove sensitive information, there must be a particularly compelling reason to preserve it.